

Disease Understanding and Visualization of Drug Repurposing Hypotheses

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Abstract. The increasing availability of biomedical data has opened new opportunities to rethink how diseases are modeled and how drug repurposing hypotheses can be systematically generated. In this context, we present a web-based platform that (i) provides access to previously integrated heterogeneous biomedical data and (ii) enables interactive visualization of disease understanding relationships, as well as of drug repurposing hypotheses. The platform constructs multilayer disease networks, visualizes disease relationships, and implements six complementary computational repurposing methods, including more naive methods, network-based analysis, and artificial intelligence-based approaches. It also provides the web services needed to access the whole set of data. This paper describes the underlying data sources and methodologies and demonstrates its capabilities through a representative visualization case.

Keywords: Drug Repurposing · Disease Understanding · Graph Neural Networks · Network Medicine · Visualization Platform

1 Introduction

Drug repurposing, the identification of new therapeutic applications for existing medications, has emerged as a promising strategy to accelerate drug development while reducing associated risks and costs. Effective implementation of drug repurposing requires computational platforms capable of integrating heterogeneous biomedical data and producing hypothesis-generating outputs. In this context, the Medical Data Analytics Laboratory (MEDAL), based at the Centro de Tecnología Biomédica (CTB) of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, has developed the DRIVE platform³.

DRIVE, short for *Data-dRiven platform for dIsease Visualization and drug rEpurposing*, addresses these challenges by leveraging multi-layered biomedical knowledge and a suite of complementary computational models. The platform

³ <https://live.drive-project.com/>

facilitates the visualization of disease-related relationships and the generation of drug repurposing hypotheses, serving as a valuable resource for academic researchers, clinical professionals, and pharmaceutical stakeholders alike. This platform has been partially developed thanks to the efforts of the GRENADA project, which serves as a proof of concept for technology transfer stemming from the DISNET research project, described in the next section.

2 DISNET Knowledge Base

The foundation of DRIVE is the knowledge base derived from the DISNET project⁴, which aggregated disease-related structured and unstructured data from public sources. DISNET models diseases as interconnected entities linked to symptoms, genes, drugs, biological pathways, and so on. This database consists of three main layers including (i) the phenotypic (which contains diseases and their related symptoms extracted from textual sources [4]), (ii) the biologic (with diseases and their associations to genes, biological pathways, ncRNAs...), and (iii) the pharmacologic layer (integrating drug-related information). These layers allow DRIVE to navigate complex biological relationships and build a data-rich foundation for inference. From these data, by applying the methods detailed in the following section, we generate different repurposing hypotheses.

3 Computational Drug Repurposing Methods

We have put forward a set of methodologies with the final aim of generating drug repurposing hypotheses. Each methodology receives as input either a disease, either a drug, either a disease-drug pair. These methodologies are all computational but have different scientific foundations and parameters:

- Information paths. Originally developed for COVID-19, this methodology leverages a total of four multi-hop information paths from symptoms or genes to drugs through different biomedical entities [8].
- Threshold values. Based on disease-gene and disease-phenotype associations, this methodology uses previously determined significance association scores from known successful repurposing cases [9].
- Pathways. This methodology exploits the potential of biological pathways instead of target genes as key elements for effective repurposing [7].
- Disease pathways. Extending the previous methodology, this one explores the overlaps in pathway-level disease mechanisms [6].
- Graph Neural Networks (GNNs). We include several models trained to predict disease-drug links using graph-based embeddings [5,1,2].
- Network-based proximity. It measures the distance between disease modules and drug targets in the interactome [3,10].

⁴ <https://disnet.ctb.upm.es/>

4 Visualization Platform

The platform offers an interactive web interface, designed for both researchers and developers. Users can explore the relationships between diseases and other biomedical entities, in the section called “Disease understanding”. In the “Drug Repurposing” section, users can obtain, filter and sort drug repurposing predictions by confidence scores or supporting evidence. The platform includes a “multi-search” function to query multiple repurposing models simultaneously. We depict this functionality in Figure 1, where we show the query for a particular disease example: Colorectal Carcinoma.

Fig. 1. Multi-search view of drug repurposing hypotheses for the particular case of Colorectal Carcinoma.

5 Conclusions and Future Works

We have presented a platform designed to facilitate the visualization and exploration of drug repurposing hypotheses. In addition to its interactive interface, the platform offers access to both the predicted repurposing candidates and the underlying data used for their generation. These hypotheses are produced by a suite of complementary computational methodologies, encompassing naive-rule-based, network-driven, and GNN-based approaches. It is intended to support a broad spectrum of users, including researchers, clinicians, and pharmaceutical professionals, enabling hypothesis testing, method benchmarking, and translational research.

Future work will focus on enhancing the platform’s analytical capabilities. Planned extensions include the integration of patient-level data and the development of interpretability modules to better explain model outputs, including a validation layer that incorporates large language models to automatically assess repurposing hypotheses by mining and summarizing supporting evidence from biomedical literature. A key upcoming feature will be the inclusion of a meta-model that combines the outputs of the existing repurposing strategies into a unified prediction.

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